

Exploring challenges to sustainability in the provision of ecosystem services by upland forests in Scotland and Ukraine

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Introduction

Contemporary societies expect a range of services to be delivered from mountain ecosystems. Their growing societal importance is clearly reflected in policies. The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (2005) states that people are integral parts of ecosystems and that a dynamic interaction exists between them and other parts of ecosystems. This approach encompasses social, economic and environmental interactions, and the dynamics and cross scale issues that have multiple outcomes. However, multi-functionality is a challenge since the combination of ecosystem services may be very different across different locations and contexts, and dependent on a high number of factors. Stakeholder priorities with respect to individual ecosystem services may also be variable, as may be a range of stakeholders (Sarkki et al., 2015). Reflexive, participatory and multilevel governance, in a continuous process of its adjustment needs to be developed to enable decision-makers to consider existing opinions and behavioural patterns of the diverse stakeholders who drive contemporary changes in remote rural areas, and respond to them (Nijnik and Miller, 2014).

Social innovation (SI) responds to social demands that are traditionally not addressed by markets or existing institutions. It includes new institutional environments (e.g. of formal and informal rules) and arrangements (spatial and procedural), related actors' relationships and interactions (e.g. new attitudes, collaborations, values, behaviours, skills, practices and learning processes) and new fields of activity (e.g. social entrepreneurship, social enterprises). Aiming at improving human wellbeing, SI creates new responses to pressing social demands which affect the process of social interactions. SI manifests itself in new social relationships and collaborations (e.g. processes, interactions, networks), while governance mechanisms based on new social networks advance social capital and can create new SIs (Nijnik et al., 2015).

Social innovations and connected new governance mechanisms can be macro or micro, structural or local, vertical (supply chains) or horizontal (regional), introduced by entrepreneurs and through solidarity, and/or by institutional changes or/and policy reforms (Nussbaumer and Moulaert,

2007). However, whatever is their nature, context or scale, they strengthen actors' ability to respond to societal challenges, such as poverty, food security, and climate change etc. (Lehtonen, 2004). Therefore, SI and enhanced governance are crucial for transition towards Sustainable Development (SD) and for enhancement of smart and inclusive growth of communities living and working in upland woodlands.

Material and Method

This paper seeks to advance both conceptual and practical knowledge and to provide guidance towards solving the problem of implementing the sustainable provision of ecosystem services from Scottish uplands and Ukrainian Carpathian Mountains into stakeholder considerations and policy-making decisions. Research follows a semi-qualitative route. It applies 'face-to-face' questionnaire surveys of respondents and the subsequent application of quantitative methods to identify, analyse and explain a range of attitudes and perspectives, among these respondents (i.e. representatives of local communities and forestry associated stakeholders), regarding multi-functional present and future of forestry in both Scotland uplands and the Ukraine's Carpathians. Stakeholder evaluation involves the application of Q-methodology, i.e. a technique that combines qualitative, participatory approaches, and discourse and concourse analyses, with quantitative, correlation and factor analytical research tools to explore existing challenges for developing multi-functional forestry in the analysed case studies.

Results

The prevailing attitudes of forestry associated stakeholders and local people towards the place of woodlands in livelihoods of the communities living in study areas and the role of woodland development in raising of their well-being were analysed. Stakeholder attitudes concerning access of local communities to obtaining forest multiple ecosystem services, including wood and non-timber forest products, and services, and a range of options for changes in forest policy formulation and implementation, were examined. Important criteria reflecting respondents' perspectives were identified and key factors influencing the attitudinal diversity explained. Findings imply why certain

aspects of the forestry policy, governance and management decisions are unfavourably viewed by some people, and favourably received by others. Results of the analysis carried out in Ukraine show that in a broad sense the economic, environmental, social, cultural and aesthetic functions of forests contribute considerably to the well-being of forest-dependent communities in the vicinity of the Carpathian Mountains; while illegal logging is among the main threats to a sustainable provision of forest ecosystem services and the well-being of communities living in the uplands (Melnykovych and Soloviy, 2014). It is concluded that the innovative sustainable forest management practices, community-based management strategies, smart development of forest-dependent mountain territories could contribute to increasing of human well-being and strengthening of community resilience, without threatening sustainability of fragile mountain ecosystems.

Results from Scotland improved an understanding of how the diversity of opinions on forestry changes could influence the selection and evaluation of sustainable forest policy measures (Nijnik and Mather, 2008). The different importance accorded by respondents to the integration of woodlands in rural landscapes, made us aware of public priorities and of factors that can hamper ecosystem based adaptation policies and management practices. At times, entirely opposite attitudes towards forestry practices and the key objectives of the future of forestry in uplands were revealed. However, interviewed people from both countries put strong emphasis on native woodlands regeneration. Attention of respondents is paid to the recognition of the importance of biodiversity conservation and nature preservation, of forest multi-functionality, and people's rights to enjoy the beauty of landscapes. More specific attitudes, the heterogeneity of existing perspectives, and commonalities and differences across stakeholder groups were identified and explained. The general conclusion signified the consensus on an important role of woodlands for the development of upland areas, as offering a range of benefits to people, to the environment and the economy.

Discussion

Our methodological approach went beyond a traditional analysis of public attitudes, as it tend to identify and explain a variety of factors influencing the decision-making, for which our consultation with stakeholders was the first step in promoting of their engagement in decision-making. Selected findings from this paper concerning the heterogeneity of attitudes or on improved

participation in decision-making could be of help in preventing and/or resolving potential conflicts and in designing policy measures addressing sustainability in the provision of ecosystems services (including of non-wood forest products) by upland forests and better targeting of forest management decisions. An important question that merits further attention is how to multiply synergies and balance trade-offs (e.g. between forestry and farming; between woodlands expansion and nature restoration; between woody biomass for energy production and ecological sustainability). Also, fostering resilience of upland ecosystems and enhancing their sustainable development necessitate the establishment of an appropriate institutional framework and the encouraging of social innovations, especially with regard to multipurpose forestry, which is likely to be more attractive to people as it can provide additional benefits and can promote sustainable development in marginalised rural areas.

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